

Biopsychosocial predictors of self-regulation in school-aged children

List of articles included in the *Narrative review of psychosocial determinants of self-regulation in school-aged children*

1. Cross-sectional studies

1. Babarro, I., Ibarluzea, J., Theodorsson, E., Fano, E., Lebeña, A., Guxens, M., Sunyer, J., & Andiarena, A. (2023). Hair cortisol as a biomarker of chronic stress in preadolescents: Influence of school context and bullying. *Child Neuropsychology*, 29(5), 742–759.
2. Burani, K., Brush, C. J., Spahr, C., Slavich, G. M., Meyer, A., & Hajcak, G. (2023). Corporal Punishment Is Uniquely Associated With a Greater Neural Response to Errors and Blunted Neural Response to Rewards in Adolescence. *Biological Psychiatry: Cognitive Neuroscience and Neuroimaging*, 8(2), 210–218.
3. Costa, M., Tagliabue, S., Melim, B., Mota, C. P., & Matos, P. M. (2022). *Adolescents' attachment, quality of relationships with residential caregivers, and emotion regulation*. *Journal of Adolescence*, 94(5), 703–717.
4. Clem, A.-L., Rudasill, K. M., Hirvonen, R., Aunola, K., & Kiuru, N. (2021). *The roles of teacher–student relationship quality and self-concept of ability in adolescents' achievement emotions: Temperament as a moderator*. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 36(2), 263–286.
5. Cumming, M. M., Qiu, Y., Oblath, R., Frazier, S. L., Criado, C., Theodore, S., & Placido, G. (2024). Perceived Stress, Executive Function, and Stress Regulation: Implications for Middle Schoolers' Emotional and Behavioral Well-being. *Remedial and Special Education*. Advance online publication.
6. Deffaa, M., Weis, M., Muñoz, L., & Trommsdorff, G. (2022). The Role of Culture and Contextual Risk for Maternal Parenting and Children's Behavior Regulation in Chile and Germany. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 31(9), 2472–2490.
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9. Hamama, L., & Hamama-Raz, Y. (2021). Meaning in Life, Self-Control, Positive and Negative Affect: Exploring Gender Differences Among Adolescents. *Youth & Society*, 53(5), 699–722.

10. Jandrić, S., Kovač, V., Kovač, D., & Degmecic, D. (2023). Self-Regulation and Rumination as Transdiagnostic Factors for Internalizing and Externalizing Disorders Among Adolescents. *Clinical Neuropsychiatry*, 20(5), 415–423.
11. Jiang, M., Gao, K., Wu, Z., & Guo, P. (2022). The influence of academic pressure on adolescents' problem behavior: Chain mediating effects of self-control, parent–child conflict, and subjective well-being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. [Article number/page range missing]
12. Kaczmarek, M., & Trambacz-Oleszak, S. (2021). School-Related Stressors and the Intensity of Perceived Stress Experienced by Adolescents in Poland. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(22), 11791.
13. Kengatharan, N., & Gnanarajan, A. H. (2023). Teacher self-efficacy and student misbehaviour: The moderating role of gender–classroom management. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 37(2), 507–525.
14. Klassen, R. M., Krawchuk, L. L., & Rajani, S. (2008). Academic procrastination of undergraduates: Low self-efficacy to self-regulate predicts higher levels of procrastination. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 33(4), 915–931.
15. Kurtović, A., Vrdoljak, G., & Hirnstein, M. (2021). Contribution to family, friends, school, and community is associated with fewer depression symptoms in adolescents—Mediated by self-regulation and academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11.
16. Marengo, D., Fabris, M. A., Prino, L. E., Settanni, M., & Longobardi, C. (2021). Student-teacher conflict moderates the link between students' social status in the classroom and involvement in bullying behaviors and exposure to peer victimization. *Journal of Adolescence*, 87, 86–97.
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20. Reyad, A. M., Yehia, A. A., & Elwan, F. Z. (2023). The Factorial Structure of Self-Regulation from Late Childhood to Adolescence: A Gender Perspective. *American Journal of Applied Psychology, 12*(1).
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24. Szempruch, J. (2018). Feeling of Professional Burnout in Teachers of Secondary Schools. *The New Educational Review, 54*(1), 219–230.
25. Szymańska, A., & Aranowska, E. (2021). Parental stress in the relationship with the child and personality traits that parents shape in their children. *Early Child Development and Care, 191*(2), 198–209.
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28. Yang, X., Li, R., Du, L., Cui, W., & Sun, C. (2023). Father’s parenting attitude and teacher–child relationships: Mediating role of children’s self-regulation ability. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*.
29. Zhao, J., Wu, M., Wu, L., Hou, H., Xie, J., Su, C., Li, X., & Wu, J. (2024). Parental mindful parenting and adolescent resilience: The chain mediating role of self-compassion and emotion regulation. *Current Psychology, 43*(41).

2. Longitudinal studies

1. Afifi, T. O., Fortier, J., Sareen, J., & Taillieu, T. (2019). Associations of Harsh Physical Punishment and Child Maltreatment in Childhood With Antisocial Behaviors in Adulthood. *JAMA Network Open, 2*(1), e187374.

2. Allen, J. P., Costello, M. A., Hellwig, A. F., Pettit, C., Stern, J. A., & Uchino, B. N. (2023). Adolescent Caregiving Success as a Predictor of Social Functioning from Age 13 to 33. *Child Development, 94*(6), 1610–1624.
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7. Bolger, M. A., Meldrum, R. C., & Liu, L. (2022). Maternal Low Self-Control, Maternal Attachment Toward Children, Parenting Practices, and Adolescent Low Self-Control: A Prospective 15-Year Study. *Journal of Developmental and Life-Course Criminology, 8*(2), 206–231.
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9. Brody, G. H., Yu, T., Miller, G. E., & Chen, E. (2020). A family-centered prevention ameliorates the associations of low self-control during childhood with employment income and poverty status in young African American adults. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, 61*(4), 425–435.
10. Busching, R. (2024). Do peers matter? The influence of peers’ self-regulation on individual self-regulation: A longitudinal multilevel analysis. *Frontiers in Developmental Psychology*.
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maternal responsiveness and self-regulation. *Developmental Psychology*, 48(6), 1529–1539.

14. Dollar, J. M., Perry, N. B., Calkins, S. D., Shanahan, L., Keane, S. P., Shriver, L., & Wideman, L. (2023). Longitudinal associations between specific types of emotional reactivity and psychological, physical health, and school adjustment. *Development and Psychopathology*, 35(2), 509–523.
15. Dou, K., Wang, L.-X., Cheng, D.-L., Li, Y.-Y., & Zhang, M.-C. (2022). Longitudinal association between poor parental supervision and risk-taking behavior: The role of self-control and school climate. *Journal of Adolescence*, 94(4), 525–537.
16. Duckworth, A. L., Kim, B., & Tsukayama, E. (2012). Life stress impairs self-control in early adolescence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 3, 608.
17. Engels, M. C., Spilt, J., Denies, K., & Verschueren, K. (2021). The role of affective teacher-student relationships in adolescents' school engagement and achievement trajectories. *Learning and Instruction*, 75, 101485.
18. Fergusson, D. M., Boden, J. M., & Horwood, L. J. (2013). Childhood self-control and adult outcomes: Results from a 30-year longitudinal study. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 52(7), 709–717.e1.
19. Guyer, A. E., Jarcho, J. M., Pérez-Edgar, K., Degnan, K. A., Pine, D. S., Fox, N. A., & Nelson, E. E. (2015). Temperament and Parenting Styles in Early Childhood Differentially Influence Neural Response to Peer Evaluation in Adolescence. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 43(5), 863–874.
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22. Hughes, J. N., & Cao, Q. (2018). Trajectories of teacher-student warmth and conflict at the transition to middle school: Effects on academic engagement and achievement. *Journal of School Psychology*, 67, 148–162.
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24. Husby, S. M., Skalická, V., Li, Z., Belsky, J., & Wichstrøm, L. (2023). Reciprocal Relations Between Conflicted Student-teacher Relationship and Children's Behavior Problems: Within-person Analyses from Norway and the USA. *Research on Child and Adolescent Psychopathology*, 51(3), 331–342.

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3. Theoretical / conceptual reviews

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